

Usage Patterns of Western Televised Contents in Pakistan: A Use and Gratification Approach

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Abstract *The main objective of the research was to find out the preference wise list of western televised programming among the viewers in Islamabad. By applying the stratified sampling technique, 292 respondents were finalized for analysis. It was found that entertainment programming was mostly consumed western televised contents and then, educational and political. The usage of western televised contents was assessed due to dissatisfaction about their own programming, educational and political systems. They preferred the western programming and systems comparatively a better choice.*

Key Words

dissatisfaction, exposure, educational, entertainment, political, usage.

Introduction

Televised contents of the western media have remained a theoretical phenomenon in the field of mass communication. Many of the researchers have focused on the usage and various effects of western televised contents in the developing countries. The people use western televised contents to become adequate with new trends and to become globally socialized. In this process, people change their perceptions in accordance with the contents and meanwhile, act upon.

Pakistan being a developing country is supposed to be more affected by the western televised contents. Starting from the notion that is generally observed as “it does not happen in the west” mentioning every goodwill and happenings with the west although no one has visited any western country. The research becomes more important in these special circumstances to dig out the usage patterns and cultural effects of western televised contents. By the start of private television media in 2001, the consumption of western televised content has increased massively in Pakistan. Rapidly change in promoting foreign social taboos among the people is assessed. People like to adopt the western way of life and are observed talking in favor of western culture. Moreover, more inclination towards the west is observed with more education and resources.

Concerns are when it is said that the time has been changed and the patterns of life are mentioned from the various western televised programs. People choose different western programs to be well aware of globalized world and become leaders among their social groups. It enables social taboos to insert in the society as well.

It is also a matter of concern to dig out the trends in changing perceptions as the result of exposure to western televised contents. Massive demand for cable network highlights the importance of western televised contents as the cable network is known for the western network. The huge shifting of the viewers towards foreign programming is the base for this research. The cable network is seen in the areas even general necessities of life do not. Following the western actors and English medium education are the indicators of this shift.

When a perceived culture dominates in the minds of viewers of foreign televised contents, they struggle to get that in their lives. They work more to get money and resources to become able to buy the products enabling their access to the culture of foreign televised contents. They are found in markets searching the new fashions as shown in the contents of those television channels. They are becoming

more modern as compared to their past norms and values and consider the modern life of foreign as their idols. The basis of research becomes more valuable in Pakistan when it is assessed that the majority of Pakistani people have not gone or visit the countries of the developed world.

Media in Pakistan

Private media in Pakistan with addition to cable networks has developed a new scenario of western televised programming. The investment of billions in the media industry is a clear indication of public demand. Massive revenue of the foreign televised programming in Pakistan claims the importance and huge viewership of the contents. It was reported that the advertising revenue was reached approximately 32 billion rupees in 2011-12 (Gallup Pakistan, 2012). In a country like Pakistan, it is a huge amount and the field is researchable.

Uses and Gratification

The audience is not passive but reactive. They choose the televised programming as per their own needs. The theory was formulated by Jay Blumler and Denis McQuail in 1969 who differentiated the audience in various categories. They assessed the motivations for which people watched political programs during the 1964 presidential elections UK. (Katz, E., Blumler, J.G., & Gurevitch, M. 1973)

The authors suggested that media empowers the people to become a knowledgeable person of the society although selected by themselves. The effects are self-determined. The effect can be media-oriented or entirely opposite of what the sender intended.

Implications of Role of Foreign Media

Researchers of social sciences assessed that communication was not the only purpose of western media in developing countries of Africa and Asia. It was assessed while conducting the interviews of the viewers of soap operas that they sought three kinds of gratification i.e. emotional, wishful thinking and learning (Herta Hertzong, 1944). It was further realized that people use various kinds of televised content to get out of a certain form of media. (Wilbur Schramm, 1954)

Jay Blumler and Denis McQuail (1969) studied usage patterns of certain televised political programs during UK elections 1964. The motivation levels among the viewers were assessed. Later on, Jay Blumler, Joseph Brown and Denis McQuail resulted in four types of media usage i.e. diversion, personal relationships, personal identity and surveillance. Furthermore, the same researchers conducted six collaborative types of research in 1974 to dig out the usage patterns of mass media among the viewers.

Statement of the problem

Massive usage of western televised contents has been assessed in Pakistan since the last decade after the invention of private television channels and availability of cable networks. Many of the people are observed telling them about the various contents of western televised channels. The educated people have set a pattern of communication and life as highlighted in the various programs of western televised contents. The more accessibility has generated dissatisfaction about their own contents and meanwhile, they are more inclined towards the foreign contents.

West is perceived as a modern world to be followed. To become modern, it is essential to follow the foreign norms and values and television media has become a vital tool in diffusing their patterns and making them acceptable in our lives. With the time, media effects are increasing and also taking new dimensions. Big media conglomerates in Pakistan are shaping their own contents according to western content. Besides all, more educated people have shifted themselves to foreign media channels and they become the models for local nationals. Following that class of society, harmful effects can be assessed on local culture and national identity as well.

To reach out to the effects on the viewers, it is essential to dig out the patterns of western televised media and the various characteristics of the viewers. The main objective of the research will be carried out by keeping an eye on the problem statement.

Rationale of Research

Television has remained a major consumed media tool in Pakistan. Gallup (2017) reported that almost 8 million households had the access to cable TV in 2009. The report further explored that TV viewers spent 2 hours daily on average. Entertainment programs were referred to most consumed TV programs with 64% preference. High viewership requires investigation of the effects of the television channels.

The phenomenon of uses and gratification has been researched immensely all over the world. In media changing circumstances, it has equal importance nowadays in Pakistan. The research will be helpful to distinguish

the various elements of the society in terms of their preferences of western televised contents. Moreover, UNESCO has reported that 75% of the total foreign programming is diffused through television. The research becomes more important in the given circumstances.

Research Objectives

1. To dig out the various western media usage patterns.
2. To find out the demographic characteristics of the viewers of western televised contents.
3. To analyze the role of education in giving preference to various types of western televised contents.
4. To comprise the likeness level of the local televised contents among the viewers.

Hypotheses

H1: More exposure to western televised contents more trust over foreign entertainment programming.

H2: More exposure to western televised contents more trust over the foreign educational system.

H3: More exposure to western televised contents more trust over the foreign political system.

Literature Review

Okafor Samuel Okechi (2017) resulted that exposure to foreign televised contents had contributed negatively to the development of local cultural norms and values among the viewers in Africa. The authors analyzed that more exposure to foreign televised contents had resulted in declination of their own culture among the viewers. The viewers were found more reluctant to own their norms and values as they had developed an imaginary world in accordance to expose foreign contents. The target audience was the children who became less confident and did not able to develop their own personality as they considered themselves backward and a massive sense of self-hatred was found. The study is more relevant to users and gratification phenomenon as the effects of the exposure may lead to a total collapse of the local system. The author suggested that the parents or whoever had the responsibility to the upbringing of children should be more careful as the foreign televised contents made an environment to accept or reject social norms and values.

Thomas E. Ruggiero (2000) argued that uses and gratification were the phenomena to be understood and implementable in mass communication. He stated that the theory had always provided a cutting edge theoretical approach in the initial stages of each new mass communication medium including television. He was with the view that researchers should be willing to explore the interpersonal and qualitative aspects of mediated communication.

McQuail (1994) inserted that the actual phenomenon of uses and gratification was a sub-tradition of media effects. Cantril (1942) highlighted the importance of various types of televised contents explored by the viewers to gratify their needs.

Ostman and Jeffer's (1980) realized the association between television viewing motivations and the potential for lifestyle traits for predictions. Bantz's (1982) argued that the selection of televised programs have affected the viewer's perceptions massively while some of the researchers had comparatively analyzed the alternative gratification models (Rayburn's, 1985). Windahl (1981) concluded that the viewers were more affected while selecting different televised programs. The author suggested that the content analysis mediated by use might be the right choice to be analyzed. Webster and Wakshlag (1983) assessed the interchange between programming structures, content preferences and viewing conditions in the program choice process. Furthermore, Dobos (1992) described that the viewers chose foreign televised contents for their own satisfaction. A factor of dissatisfaction about their own contents might be a reason behind the selection of foreign televised contents.

Williams et al. (1988) defined demassification as the control of the individual over the medium, "which likens the new media to face-to-face interpersonal communication". The author further stated that the accessibility to various types of televised contents was the main reason behind the selection. Chamberlain (1994) gave more importance to a viewer by having accessibility to choose from a large selection of media. The author further elaborated that the inclusion of new technologies had enabled the viewers to tailor messages to their needs. Kuehn (1994) while citing The New York Times, emphasized that the selection of various contents of any news was easy with the accessibility of new technology. He comprised those had paid the total amount for a newspaper copy and those who selected some versions on the internet according to their own needs. He concluded that the new technology in the media industry had enabled the viewers more to select the contents according to their needs.

Research Methodology

The research was carried out in Islamabad, a city with more access to technology and supposed to be inclined to westernized norms and values. 292 respondents were selected randomly by dividing the whole city into 7 blocks

as in general elections. 50 questionnaires were distributed among the respondents from each block. The less filled responses were not included for the sample to be analyzed. The reliability of the desired variables was tested and found satisfactory. The survey method is very useful to carry out a research of a portion or sample acquired from the whole population. Meanwhile, generalizing the results is very common and useful in survey research as the sample described all the population of the city. The survey method contributes to answer the questions about how a large number of subjects feel, behave, or are, especially with regard to variables that change over time (James W. Tankard, Jr., 1992). The survey was distributed among the respondents after asking a verbally asked question that whether they had visited any western country if no, then he/she was selected for the research. They were further asked about their habits of western televised contents and accessibility. The idea was based upon actual linkage of exposure to western televised contents and their usage patterns.

Analyzing of Survey

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) is very useful and is specially designed to analyze the data in social sciences studies. The analysis was carried out by using a Likert scale and SPSS to measure the responses of respondents. The respondents were asked to mark a suitable scale against each question and that established a unit of analysis. The whole population of Islamabad having the above-mentioned characteristics was considered as the sampling frame. The stratified sampling technique used to formulate the desired sampling design. The strata were functionalized by using the census details and the division of the city as per criteria by Capital Development Authority (CDA). The method of equal representation of all strata was applied. The census (2017) concluded almost equal representation of males and females in terms of the number of population.

Variables and Conceptualization

Exposure to western televised contents was observed as an independent variable for the study. To define, a pilot study was done and an open-ended question about their preference of western televised contents and then they merged into three main categories i.e. entertainment programs included of film, drama, songs and comedy, educational programs included of perceptions about western education and educational system and political programs included of perceptions about western politics and political system. On the other hand, dissatisfaction level about their own entertainment programming, educational and political systems were assessed and linked to analyze the results.

Results and Discussion

The data was entered into SPSS with great care. The descriptive analysis found that entertainment was most consumed western televised contents (55.8%) and educational programming remained on second in preferred western televised contents (15.1%) meanwhile, the respondents who consumed entertainment and educational programming both (15.1%) were assessed on next. The analysis clearly indicates the consumption of political programming (4.8%) far away from both.

(Figure-1)

The results concluded that 56.6% of the male and 54.8% of the female respondents preferred entertainment programming meanwhile, 14.5% and 15.9% selected educational respectively. 5.6% of the female respondents were inclined towards political and 4.2% of the male respondents.

(Figure-2)

6.8% of the respondents with their less age and exposure were inclined to educational, 35.6% liked entertainment and only 2.3% were in favor of political programming and, 6.8%, 14.4% and 1.4% respectively as above with their age 24-29 meanwhile, 5.4%, 4.5% and 1.4% respectively. The greater exposure explored that was assessed with the inclusion of political programming. The results concluded that young people with less exposure used the foreign programming for educational and entertainment purposes while with the greater in age and exposure, a likeness for political programming was observed.

(Figure-3)

How much time you spent watching foreign television a day=1 Hour or below

(Figure-4)

How much time you spent watching foreign television a day=2-4 Hours

(Figure-5)

The analysis showed that 13.4% of the respondents who preferred educational programming with the time spent one hour or below a day were graduate, 3.4% of the same time spent and education liked political, 47.9% were inclined to entertainment and 10.1% of the category preferred educational and entertainment foreign programming. Meanwhile, the

(Figure-6)

graduates who spent 2-4 hours a day with the foreign content preferred entertainment 10.1% and graduates who spent more than 4 hours a day were inclined to entertainment. The respondents who were master degree holders with one hour or less time spent preferred entertainment programming 47.3%, among the same education level who spent 2-4 hours answered in favor of entertainment 12.7% and the master degree holders who spent more than 4 hours a day were found consistent with entertainment programming.

(Figure-7)

(Figure-8)

Furthermore, the respondents who had above master level degree with one hour or less time spent preferred entertainment 32.2% and educational 15.3%. In addition to the same education category who spent 2-4 hours a day with the foreign content preferred entertainment 8.5% and political 2.5% programming and who spent more

(Figure-9)

(Figure-10)

than 4 hours a day were found inclined to the entertainment programming. The results concluded no difference in the selection of programming with respect to the education and time spent of the respondents. The rearrangement of data as per the required analysis found that 38.7% among with their age 23 or below assumed the foreign entertainment programming better than the local programming and 31.4% disagreed, 4.1% with their age 24-29 agreed and 2.9% disagreed while 13.5% with their age above 29 agreed and 24.3% among them were against the statement. Meanwhile, 18.5% among the female with their age 23 or below agreed and 17.1% disagreed of the same age group, the female respondents with their age 24-29 years 18.9% assumed the foreign entertainment programming better than the local and 20% did not agree, 6.3% with their age above 29 agreed and 1.3% disagreed.

(Figure-11)

(Figure-12)

The analysis found that 39.9% of the male respondents with their age 23 or below agreed that the foreign political system was better and 22.4% disagreed, 4.1% with their age 24-29 agreed and 2% disagreed, 16% with their age above 29 agreed and 16.3% disagreed. Moreover, 16.9% of the female respondents with their age 23 or less agreed and 24.5% disagreed, 17.7% with their age 24-29 agreed and 26.5% disagreed, 5.3% with their age above 29 5.3% agreed and 8.2% disagreed.

The results found that the male respondents with their age 23 or below, 39.5% agreed that the western education system was better than local and 17.6% disagreed, 3.9% with their age 24-29 agreed and 2.9% disagreed, 16.3% agreed and 14.7% disagreed. Furthermore, 16.3% of the female respondents with their age 23 or below agreed and 32.4% disagreed, 18.2% with age 24-29 agreed and 26.5% disagreed, 5.8% replied in favor of foreign education with their age above 29 while 5.9% disagreed.

It was explored that 33.3% (75) of the male respondents with their age 23 or below agreed that Pakistani culture should adopt new cultural artifacts to meet the requirement of the world, 49.3% disagreed, 4.4% with their age 24-29 agreed and 1.5% disagreed, 16% with their age above 29 agreed and 16.4% disagreed.

(Figure-13)

(Figure-14)

Meanwhile, among the female respondents, 17.8% agreed with their age 23 or below and 19.4% disagreed, 21.8% (49) agreed and 10.4% with their age 24-29 disagreed, 6.7% with their age above 29 agreed and 3% disagreed.

It was further assessed that 39% of the male respondents with their age 23 or below agreed that their culture had not fulfilled their needs and 34.6% disagreed, 4.4% with their age 24-29 agreed and 3% disagreed, 17.6% with their age above 29 agreed and 14.3% disagreed. Meanwhile, 16.4% of the female respondents agreed and 20.3% disagreed, 18.2% with their age 24-29 agreed and 20.3% disagreed, 4.4% with above 29 age agreed and 7.5% disagreed.

(Figure-15)

(Figure-16)

The analysis found that 41.4% of the male respondents with their satisfactory income agreed that foreign entertainment programming was far better than the local programming, 35.7% disagreed and 14.9% with their high income agreed and 22.9% disagreed. The analysis of female respondents for the same category found that 30.6% agreed and 27.1% disagreed with their income status satisfactory while 13.1% agreed and 14.3% disagreed with their income status high.

(Figure-17)

(Figure-18)

The results explored that among the male, 44% with their satisfactory income were inclined to in favor of the foreign political system and 20.4% disagreed, 16% among them with their high income preferred the foreign political system and 20.4% did not prefer. Moreover, 27.2% of the female respondents with their satisfactory income preferred foreign political system and 42.9% were not inclined to that, 12.8% with their high income agreed and 16.3% disagreed.

(Figure-19)

(Figure-20)

Hypotheses Testing

The Spearman’s correlation with the 0.05 level of significance concluded a positive relationship between exposure to western televised contents and entertainment programming.

Table 1. Correlation between Exposure and Trust on Foreign Entertainment Programming

		Time spent	Entertainment
Spearman's rho	Coefficient	1.000	.266 ^a
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.20
	N	292	292
	Cor. Coefficient	.266 ^a	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.20	.
	N	292	292

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The regression analysis resulted that exposure explained 32% of the variance in trust about western entertainment programming.

Table 2. Regression Analysis between Exposure and Trust on Foreign Entertainment Programming (Model Summaryb)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.217 ^a	.32	.029	.178

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Time spent
- b. Dependent Variable: Entertainment

Furthermore, $F(1,290) = 3.84 < 5.436$ at a 5% level of significance observed that the observed value did not fall in the critical region hence H1 was accepted.

Table 3. F Analysis between Exposure and Trust on Foreign Entertainment Programming

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.979	1	.979	5.436	.000 ^a
	Residual	52.240	290	.180		
	Total	53.219	291			

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Time spent
- b. Dependent Variable: Entertainment

The correlation of exposure was also significant with trust in the western political system.

Table 4. Correlation between Exposure and Trust on Foreign Political System

			Time spent	Political System
Spearman's rho	Time spent	Cor. Coefficient	1.000	.256**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.380
		N	292	292
	Political system	Cor. Coefficient	.256**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.380	.
		N	292	292

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

F (1,290) = 3.84 < 4.20 at 5% level of significance, proved the significance relationships between the two variables.

Table 5. F Analysis between Exposure and Trust on Foreign Political System

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.989	1	.989	4.205	.001 ^a
	Residual	39.789	290	.137		
	Total	40.777	291			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Time spent

b. Dependent Variable: Political system

The positive correlation was assessed between exposure and trust in the western educational system.

Table 6. Correlation between Exposure and Trust on Foreign Educational System

			Time spent	Education
Spearman's rho	Time spent	Cor.Coefficient	1.000	.221*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.380
		N	292	292
	Education	Cor. Coefficient	.221*	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.380	.
		N	292	292

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The significance correlation of the two variables was assessed as F (1,290) = 3.84 < 4.32 at 5% level of significance.

Discussion

The consistency in trust rate with the high exposure resulted that more exposure to the western televised contents developed a sense of satisfaction and manipulating their thought in accordance with the contents as portrayed. A huge number of the respondents were found dissatisfied by their entertainment programs, educational and political systems and hence, more inclined to the western televised contents and affected as well. The results indicated that more educated female was inclined towards political system beside male who were in favor of entertainment and educational.

Summary of Findings

The respondents consumed entertainment programming massively while educational at second. The less preference for political programming might be a result of the instability of the political system in Pakistan. More preference for the western entertainment programs might result in diversion from their level of own dissatisfaction or a result of less satisfaction with their own programs and systems.

Conclusion

The results concluded that all the respondents were in favor of western televised contents instead of differentiation in income or education. Somehow, less inclination was assessed with the greater age and income of the respondents. The results concluded that education could play a vital in descending the inclination towards the west.

It was found an alien world about the west in the minds of respondents. The negative effects can increase with the passage of time.

Furthermore, the significant correlation between the inclination towards the foreign entertainment programming and political system (Coefficient = 0.20), significant correlation between the inclination towards the foreign political and educational systems (Coefficient = 0.43) and between the political system and positivity about the foreign culture (Coefficient = 0.21) concluded that the all the programming formats mostly liked by the respondents were linked with each other. It was found that the exposure to foreign televised contents had effected the perception and attitude of the respondents in total.

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